

Paradigm Shift in Quality of Education

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Abstract

Business houses across the globe identify quality as a key competing strategy either to sustain, improve, or augment their market share, whether they are involved in manufacturing and distributing products or delivering service, or both,. Hence, industries are weighing up on generation of innovative processes using principles of quality management with a sight to design methods and procedures that effectively control and quality can be guaranteed in the quest of excellence. The vision and mission of organizations may vary, but business houses attempt to identify customer necessity and deliver goods/services of right quality that delight the customers. After 1970s, inspection activities as base for quality control practices are being dropped and replaced by quality assurance measures, and presently, many organizations sincerely work towards TQM – Total Quality Management (Dale, 1999).

In developed countries service sectors are responsible for around 75 percent of the GDP and currently, similar trend is being detected in most of the developing countries also (Mitra, 2003).

Measurement and evaluation of service quality are largely swayed by the expectations and opinions of stakeholders, as they are directly engaged in intangible delivery. Further, nature, size and internal and external constraints of the organization greatly influence service setting. Organizations concerned to implement TQM find it tough to gain a widespread implementation strategy because chain of implementation of TQM tools extensively varies among types of services provided within an industry category (Gustafsson, 2003).

Hence, it is sought to build a holistic methodology to design a tool comprising of service dimensions and items for systematic service quality appraisal. Attempt has been carried out in this paper to render a framework for designing an instrument suiting most of the stakeholders and methodology for identification of focus criteria. The choice of education sector for the present paper lies in the reality that education contributes largely to socio-economic development of a developing country like India. Also, 'Education' is primarily treated as philanthropic service.

In order to characterize services, it is not sufficient to say merely that they are intangible as distinguished from tangible goods. Many

modern products are provided in a combination of both. For example, while purchasing a motor vehicle the customer is provided services such as maintenance and repair. In order to render a suitable definition of services, it is desirable to look into the various features of a service (Hope and Muhlemann, 1997):

- Intangibility: services cannot generally be sensed through physical features.
- Inseparability: services are rendered and consumed simultaneously as they are produced.
- Variability: the quality of a service may differ on the basis of service provider.
- Perishability: opposite to goods, services cannot be retained for future use, hence, there would be no inventory.

For the development of Higher Education in India UGC was set up in India in the year 1953 in order to focus and to ensure quality education for all citizens. India has fruitfully established the world's largest educational system. The quality of many Indian higher educational institutions is recognized to be on par with the best anywhere. It has at least 550 universities level institutions and deemed to be universities, Institution or college of national importance, 35000 colleges, and over a million learners and half million faculty teachers.

India is considered a global talent pool, providing educated and qualified human resources in very large quantity to the world. This has been a primary contributor for the conversion of India as fast growing economy since liberalization. But due to non-accessibility, poverty and other hurdles the efforts of upgrading the Indian Education standards are not fruitful. Due to poverty Indian Government is unable to achieve fuller success in the implementing quality education projects. The eleventh five-year plan has improved the importance of development of education sector.

It is a growing belief that quality education is available in India, but it was also true that in recent past it was believed that even primary education is not available in India. Research work done in the past has tinted ambiguities in the curriculum and methodologies. But while in the amendments preparing the criticisms had acted upon them. That is introduction of new courses, changes in the syllabus, dynamic methodologies and many others. So that, at present infrastructure and advanced faculties are facilitating with delivery of quality content.

Indian Higher Education

According to Ronald Barnett (1992) there are four principal notions of higher education.

- i) Higher education as production tool of qualified human resource: Higher education is a system in which learners are "products" absorbed for employment in industry. Thus, higher education provides input to business and industry.
- ii) Higher education as research training: Higher education is preparing learners for becoming qualified scientists and quality from this view-point is transmission of academic thoroughness to carryout quality research.
- iii) Higher education as well-organized management of teaching profession: It is a strong belief that teaching is the heart of education. Thus, higher education institutions aim on effective management of teaching-learning process by bettering the quality of teaching, focusing on higher course completion rate.
- iv) Higher education as facilitator of improving life chances: Higher education is an opportunity for precipitation in the progression of individual values through a flexible mode of continuing education to serve the society.

Amusingly, the four concepts of higher education are not mutually exclusive, but, they are integrated to give a holistic view of higher education. If one looks at colleges and universities, it may be realized that teaching, research, extension, and management of self form the four main pinnacles of higher education.

Higher education and the Society

Higher education generally envelops teaching, research, extension and management. Higher education forms the basis of scientific and technological development and economic growth of a nation. Development of local technologies and potentials in agriculture and industrial arenas are possible only through our world-class higher education. Higher education further provides opportunities for lifelong learning, allowing people to update and upgrade their knowledge and skills from time to time based on dynamic societal needs.

The Kothari Commission (1966) listed the following functions of universities.

- To seek and cultivate novel knowledge, to engage robustly and boldly in the quest for truth, and to infer earlier knowledge and beliefs in light of fresh deeds and discoveries;
- To render apt leadership in all walks of life, to recognize gifted youth and facilitate them exploit their full potential by nurturing physical fitness, developing the mind powers and cultivating appropriate interests, attitudes, morals and intellectual values;
- To provide the community with competent human resource trained in medicine, science and technology, agriculture, arts, and other professions, who shall also be cultured individuals, imbued with sensitized social purpose;
- To promote quality and social justice, and to minimize socio-cultural distinctions through dissemination of education; and
- To promote in teachers and learners, and through them, in the society, the attitude and values required for developing the “good life” in the individuals and society.

Paradigm Shift in Higher Education

Indian graduates are performing well in the Information and Knowledge industry and presently they are advantageous in the knowledge-controlled global economy. Jobs have increased, especially in education streams that have link with knowledge industry. The Indian youth are now seeking education that is of quality and immediate utility. Private education institutions have sprouted to bridge the growing industrial demand by introducing various specific skill oriented courses. Foreign universities are also focusing to encash on such demands. The Indian economy also has revealed steady progress in recent years. This has enhanced higher percentage of families to spend additional money on education. Thus growing interest in utility focused education and improved economic strength of few have encouraged the growth of private institutions and entry of foreign universities in India. India is steadily shifting from generalized economy to a fast track of economic and industrial development, which has paved way to various paradigm shifts in the higher education field also, such as:

- From ‘State Controlled Government Education’ to an ‘Open Market Economy Education’
- From ‘Education for Personnel Development’ to ‘Education for Human Resource Development’.
- From ‘Education for a Few’ to ‘Education for Mass’.
- From ‘Indigenous’ to ‘Global Education’.
- From ‘Institution or Teacher Centred Education’ to ‘Learner Centred Education’.
- From ‘Subsidised / Free Education’ to ‘Education for a Price.’

The fact that changes in Indian higher education system is purely fast, phenomenal and inevitable is undeniable. Private institution participation in professional education, particularly technical and management education has created change in the perception of the society. The times of higher education as a subject of national policy and government regulation are fading fast. Higher Education is now globalised and a commercialized affair and the stake that the Government had in the system is greatly diminished.(Kaul,2006).

There is a shift in the focus of higher education. The focus on workplace, strategic planning, process, and outcome seem to have lost their importance. The focus on teachers and students, however, seem to have gained importance.

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